

Appendix A
 General SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping –
 Ukrainian sample

Figure A.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Ukrainian companies' sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure A.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Ukrainian companies' sustainability reporting, %

Appendix B

Kernel SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure B.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Kernel's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure B.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Kernel's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure B.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Kernel's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix C

MHP SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure C.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in MHP's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure C.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in MHP's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure C.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in MHP's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix D
Ukrlandfarming SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text
scrapping

Figure D.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Ukrlandfarming's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure D.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Ukrlandfarming's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure D.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Ukrlandfarming's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix E

Astarta SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure E.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Astarta's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure E.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Astarta's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure E.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Astarta's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix F
Continental Farmers Group SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text
scrapping

Figure F.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Continental Farmers Group 's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure F.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Continental Farmers Group's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure F.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Continental Farmers Group's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix G

EpicentrAgro SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure G.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in EpicentrAgro 's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Appendix H

Enselko SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure H.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Enselko 's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure H.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Enselko 's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure H.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Enselko's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix J

IMC SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure J.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in IMC 's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure J.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in IMC 's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure J.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in IMC's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix K

Ukrprominvest SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure K.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Ukrprominvest 's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure K.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Ukrprominvest's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure K.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Ukrprominvest's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix L

KSG SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure L.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in KSG's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure L.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in KSG's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure L.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in KSG's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix M
 General SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping –
 Finnish sample

Figure M.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Finnish companies' sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure M.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Finnish companies' sustainability reporting, %

Appendix N

Polarica SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure N.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Polarica's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure N.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Polarica's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure N.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Polarica's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix O

Hätälä Oy SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure O.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Hätälä Oy sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure O.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Hätälä Oy sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Appendix P

Nordzucker SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure P.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Nordzucker 's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure P.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Nordzucker 's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure P.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Nordzucker 's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix Q

Raisio SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure Q.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Raisio's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure Q.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Raisio's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure Q.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Raisio's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix S

Apetit SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure S.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Apetit's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure S.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Apetit's sustainability reporting, %

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure S.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Apetit's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix T

Hkscan SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure T.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Hkscans sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure T.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Hkscan's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure T.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Hkscan's sustainability reporting, %
Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix U

Fazer SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure T.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Fazer's sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure T.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Fazer's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure T.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Fazer's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix V

Valio SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure V.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Valio sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure V.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Valio's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure V.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Valio's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix W

Atria SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure W.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Atria sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)
Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure W.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Atria's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure W.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Atria's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030

Appendix X

Lantmännen SDGs disclosure characteristics detected with text scrapping

Figure X.1. Percentage of co-occurrences corresponding to each SDGs in Lantmännen sustainability reporting (in order of SDGs)

Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure X.2. Percentage of the keywords, relevant to each target SDG targets detected in Lantmännen's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via JCR SDG Mapper

Figure X.3. Word cloud on SDG-related keywords detected in Lantmännen's sustainability reporting, %
 Sources: created by the authors via Scanner 2030